

DEVELOPMENT AND CONTROL OF RESIDUAL STRESSES AND WARPAGE DURING THE ATP PROCESS

Dr. John Tierney, John W Gillespie Jr.

Center for Composite Materials

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INTRODUCTION

- Process Description
- Sources of Residual Stress and Warpage in the ATP Process
- Current Process Models
 - Simplified Residual Stress Model
 - Incremental Laminate Manufacture
 - First Ply Tension, Spring-Back Technique
- Experimental Methods
 - Measurement of Warpage During Processing
 - Control of Warpage and Residual Stresses
- Summary and Conclusions

THE AUTOMATED TAPE PLACEMENT PROCESS

The ATP process is an in-situ manufacturing technique for producing composite parts by applying heat and pressure to both an incoming tow and substrate material so that bonding is achieved at the interface, and voids are reduced in the bulk material.

Process Models for ATP

SOURCES OF RESIDUAL STRESSES IN ATP

- Coefficient of Thermal Expansion Mismatch Due to Stacking Sequence.
- Through the Thickness Temperature and Material Property Gradients.
- Sequential Lay-down and Consolidation of Plies During Manufacture.
- Temporary Non-symmetric Conditions During Manufacture.
- Panel-Tool Interactions.

SIMPLIFIED RESIDUAL STRESS MODEL

Must take a step back and see what's happening

Classical Lamination Theory:

- Thin composite panel with no out of plane displacements
- Applied to mild curvatures
- Not Including edge effects

Simple Thermal Model

Can look at the following:

- “Onion Skin Effect”
- Effects of Non-Symmetric Heating
- Temporary Unsymmetric Conditions
- Possible Methods for Warpage Manipulation?
- Provides basis for more complex/ realistic modeling in future studies
- One Catch, this approach overestimates stresses and resulting warpage due to surface ply cooling.
- Must consider some *constraining* method

INCLUSION OF PARTIAL CONSTRAINT

Summation of Load Resultants based on ply properties

$$(\Delta N_x^T, \Delta M_x^T) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \bar{Q}_{11} \Delta \varepsilon_x^T + \bar{Q}_{12} \Delta \varepsilon_x^T + \bar{Q}_{16} \Delta \varepsilon_x^T \right\} \left(\Delta z_k, \frac{\Delta z_k^2}{2} \right)$$

$$(\Delta N_y^T, \Delta M_y^T) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \bar{Q}_{12} \Delta \varepsilon_x^T + \bar{Q}_{22} \Delta \varepsilon_x^T + \bar{Q}_{26} \Delta \varepsilon_x^T \right\} \left(\Delta z_k, \frac{\Delta z_k^2}{2} \right)$$

$$(\Delta N_{xy}^T, \Delta M_{xy}^T) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \bar{Q}_{16} \Delta \varepsilon_x^T + \bar{Q}_{26} \Delta \varepsilon_x^T + \bar{Q}_{66} \Delta \varepsilon_x^T \right\} \left(\Delta z_k, \frac{\Delta z_k^2}{2} \right)$$

Partial Constraint Applied

$$\Delta N_i^T = \theta_i \Delta N_i^T$$

$$\Delta M_i^T = \theta_i \Delta M_i^T \quad (i = x, y, xy)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta \varepsilon^0 \\ \Delta \kappa^0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta N^T \\ \Delta M^T \end{bmatrix}$$

Melt Region Surrounded by Preconsolidated Material. Warpage development is reduced with increasing thickness

INTERNAL RESIDUAL STRESS

DETERMINATION OF EMPIRICAL CONSTRAINT VECTORS

- Manufacture various unconstrained composite laminates and determine final warpage.
- Determine the corresponding warpage solutions for fully constrained and unconstrained panels and compare with experimental results.
- Constraint vectors are found based on a linear dependence between final process induced warpage for constrained and unconstrained panels: i.e:

MEASUREMENT OF WARPAGE

Laser mounted on on ABB robot and measures curvature during processing (0.1mm error)

LabVIEW™ Interface

Laser Measurement System with a Labview™ Interface

Curvature Measurements

$[0^\circ/90^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$
Symmetric Laminate

$0^\circ/[90^\circ_4/0^\circ_4]$
Unsymmetric Laminate

DETERMINATION OF CURVATURE

Determine Double Derivative of Surface w.r.t. x and y directions

$$\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} = -K_x$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = -K_y$$

Carry out experiments for unconstrained panels to determine degree of partial constraint due to solid and with that data determine optimum initial loading conditions

Average slope of surface from $[90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ Laminate

Comparison of Model with Experiments

Laminate Stacking Sequence (Panel ID)	Resulting degree of constraint		Model Predictions (m ⁻¹)		Experimental results (m ⁻¹)	
	$\theta_{x,y}^n, \theta_x^m$	$\theta_{v,y}^n, \theta_v^m$	κ_x^i	κ_v^i	κ_x	κ_v
[90/0] _{2s} (1)	0.051	0.061	-0.416	-0.313	-0.427	-0.315
[90/0] _{4s} (2)	0.030	0.055	-0.236	-0.325	-0.242	-0.323
[0/90/45/-45] _s (3)	0.038	0.074	-0.413	-0.425	-0.431	-0.387
[0/90/45/-45] _{2s} (4)	0.037	0.064	-0.394	-0.416	-0.399	-0.399

Resulting constraints are quite high and fairly consistent for various stacking sequences

⊕ has direction dependence

Two Model Based Predictive Approaches

- First Ply Tension
 - Involves prestressing or pretensioning the substrate plies. The release of the laminate after manufacture results in a compressive moment which acts to restore the shape to the desired curvatures.
 - Model based search algorithm to determine optimum initial in-plane loading such that release of the laminate results in negligible warpage.
 - Must include effect of Poisson's Ratio contraction effects
 - significantly alters internal stresses.
- Spring-back Techniques
 - The final process induced curvatures are included in the design methodology of the initial tool surface.
 - Internal stresses are relaxed but mold shape may be significantly affected.

SUBSTRATE CLAMPING MECHANISM

TOP VIEW OF TABLE

- 12" Prepreg material clamped to a steel table in a cross-type configuration.
- Bi-axial loading is applied to the composite plate during the tow placement process.
- Loading is monitored and controlled during the manufacturing process
- Material can be independently loaded up to 5000 lbs. in the 90°/0° directions.

CLAMPING MECHANISM

Side view of clamp

Load Cell

- A strain gage is mounted on inner wall of a machined bolt (2 bolts used for each direction)
- Load/strain curved determined for each bolt.
- Resulting data used to monitor laminate load during the process through a Labview™ interface.

OPTIMUM FIRST PLY LOADING CONDITIONS

Model based search for optimum initial loading conditions for a $[90^\circ/0^\circ]_{4s}$ laminate

Convergence of Solution
(Effect of partial constraint included)

Prestress Loading Optimization

Panel ID.	Optimal in-plane loading(N)		Resulting Curvatures(m ⁻¹)	
	N ^m _x	N ^m _y	κ ⁱ _x	κ ⁱ _y
[90/0] _{2S}	338	341	7.73x10 ⁻⁹	-6.62x10 ⁻⁹
[90/0] _{4S}	335	552	-9.22 x10 ⁻¹⁰	-8.29 x10 ⁻⁹
[0/90/45/-45] _s	223	410	-2.99x10 ⁻⁹	1.53 x10 ⁻⁹
[0/90/45/-45] _{2s}	376	644	-2.87 x10 ⁻⁹	-1.72 x10 ⁻⁴

- Required loads are small as very little restoring strain is required for such thin composites
- Solution only applies for laminates with conform to CLT assumptions. Highly non-linear behavior cannot be included without further examination of viscoelastic relaxation.
- A similar approach with initial curvature variation results in curvatures which are the same in magnitude but opposite in sign to the final warpage from a flat panel.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

- Using classical lamination theory, a simplified residual stress model with an optimization scheme aimed at minimizing final panel curvatures was developed.
- A clamping mechanism was successfully used control the final warpage of a composite laminate which possessed thermal gradients and unsymmetric conditions during processing.
- On-line curvature measurements can be carried out using a laser measurement system installed on the ABB robot. Results from these measurements can be used to determine the degree of constraint vectors within the material.
- A combination of both spring-back control and prestressing methods can be used to control final shape. These methods can also be applied to other material systems where warpage and internal residual stresses are an issue.